

Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category saying the key “Wakalah” within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Wakalah based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 5 mapping research topics surrounding the Wakalah, namely: (1) Application of the Wakalah; (2) The effect of the Wakalah; (3) Views of Islamic law, positive law and legislation surrounding the Wakalah; (4) Efforts to develop the Wakalah; and (5) Other issues related to the Wakalah. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Wakalah, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Wakalah; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Indonesia is one of the countries with a Muslim majority in the world, which indicates the existence of sharia transactions for Indonesian Muslims. To discuss sharia-based transactions, a Islamic Financial Institution is needed as the main spearhead for Muslim citizens. Islamic Financial Institutions are a major contributor to the Indonesian economy. However, in order for this institution to develop well in the future, it requires professional management of the operating system, and must minimize the risks that will occur.

With a Islamic Financial Institution company, there will be more variety in the offers provided, resulting in Wakalahs being offered to customers. Human activity is currently still busy, so it is not uncommon for there to be certain things that cannot be done, including the operation of Islamic Financial Institutions. As a result, these activities must be represented. In relation to the activities of Islamic Financial Institutions, the Wakalah function is very important. With the times, someone who has certain limitations can represent their activities with other people who handle these activities. Wakalah is a representative agreement, giving mandate, power, or transfer of rights (power of attorney), namely an agreement to delegate power of attorney between two parties with representation. The Wakalah also means giving, handing over rights by appointment to someone, either voluntarily or in return.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding the Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion using library research. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Wakalah, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Wakalah, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

The Wakalah is a form of giving someone power to do something. According to Fatwa DSN-MUI 10/DSN-MUI/IV/2000, the Wakalah gives authority or power from the ba'i to the musytari as the recipient of the authority to purchase an item.

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and compile the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies in information science are studies that study the patterns of use of documents in literature or information sources in a particular subject. Bibliometrics consists of two types of research, namely descriptive studies and evaluative studies. Descriptive studies analyze the productivity of articles and other formats by examining authorship traits, such as the gender of the author, the type of author's work, the level of collaboration, the productivity of the institution where the author works, and the subject of the article. Evaluative studies analyze the use of created literature by counting the number of references or citations in research articles, books, or other formats. VOSviewer an improved computer program for creating and displaying bibliometric maps. Publication maps can be displayed in several ways and

functions, such as resizing, scrolling, and searching. In this way, articles can be mapped in more detail. VOSviewer presents and represents specific information about bibliometric graph maps.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Wakalah. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is a research journal article about the Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word “Wakalah” within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Wakalah based on journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Wakalahs in Islamic Financial Institutions

Search results on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) regarding Wakalahs in the period 2012 to 2022 show that there has been quite a significant increase in the last 10 years. From this search, publication data for 81 articles in accredited national journals was obtained.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Wakalah by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2012	1	2018	3
2013	3	2019	16
2014	4	2020	19
2015	3	2021	14
2016	3	2022	13
2017	2		
Total 81			

Source: Processed Data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows that there are 35 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles on Wakalahs in Islamic Financial Institutions. Al-Muamalat Journal (Journal of Sharia Economics) is the affiliate/institution publishing the most journals that publish research results on the Wakalah, namely with a total of 5 articles.

Table 2. Affiliations/ publishing institutions of Wakalah scientific publication publishers

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Amount Publication
Al-Muamalat: Journal of Sharia Economics	5
FEB Student Scientific Journal	3
AMWALUNA (Journal of Sharia Economics and Finance), At-Taradhi Journal of Economic Studies, Journal of Justisia Ekonomika: Master of Sharia Economic Law	2
ADDIN, ADLIYA: Journal of Law and Humanity, Airlangga International Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, Airlangga International Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, AL- IKTISAB Journal of Islamic Economic Law, AL IQTISHOD: Journal of Islamic Economic Thought and Research, AL-INFAQ, Al-Iqtishad: Journal of Sharia Economics, AL-MANHAJ: Journal of Islamic Law and Social Institutions, Al-Masraf: Journal of Financial and Banking Institutions, Al-Mustashfa: Research Journal of Sharia Economic Law, Al-Risala: Journal of Religious Studies and Islamic Thought, Al-Sharf: Journal of Islamic Economics, Al-Tijary, AT-TAFAHUM: Journal of Islamic Law, AT-TAWASSUTH: Journal of Islamic Economics, At-Turost : Journal of Islamic Studies, Az-Zarqa': Journal of Islamic Business Law, BANCO : Journal of Sharia Management and Banking, Diponegoro Law Review, El-Mal: Journal of Islamic Economics & Business Studies, EQUILIBRIUM, Era of Law - Scientific Journal of Legal Sciences, Indonesian Interdisciplinary Journal of Sharia Economics (IJJSE), Indonesian Notary, International Journal of Zakat, Iqtishaduna: Scientific Journal for Sharia Economic Law Students, Islam Futura, Islamic Circle, Islamic Economics Journal, Islamica: Journal of Islamic Studies, J-ESA (Jurnal of Sharia Economics), Journal of Applied Business, Taxation and Economics Research, Journal of Sharia Economics, Journal Of Social Research, Juripol (Journal of the Medan Ganesha Polytechnic Institution), Jurisdiction: Journal of Law and Sharia, Al-Hakim Journal: Student Scientific Journal, Sharia Studies, Law and Philanthropy, Al-Mizan Journal, Journal of Sharia Economics, Journal of Sharia Economics Theory and Applied, Journal of Economics, Management, Accounting and Finance, Journal of Islamic Law, MIZANI SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL: Legal, Economic and Religious Discourse, International Journal of Islamic Economics, Istiqro Journal, Journal of Management, Economics, Finance and Accounting, Legal Media Journal, Coordinates: Journal of Communication between Islamic Religious Universities, Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, Lex Renaissance, Ma'mal: Journal of Sharia and Law Laboratory, Maliyah: Journal of Islamic Business Law, Legal Issues, Legal Platform, MONETARY, MUAMALATUNA, Muttaqien,	1

loan contract, loss, month, mortgage, murabahah, musytari, object, primary data, problem, profit, purchase price, review, security, solution, sharia, third party.

- Cluster 2. Light green which covers 28 topics, namely: agreement, application, basis, book, content analysis, developer, difference, etc. mui, fatwa, fintech, government, ijarah, Indonesia, information technology, law, legal material, mudharabah, muslims, pbs, principle, project, responsibility, role, sharia investree platform, sharia principle, technique, Wakalah, wakalah bil ujah.
- Cluster 3. Blue color which covers 24 topics, namely: buyer, community, descriptive method, important role, insurance, investment, jne, library research, Malaysia, MFC, Mui, negligence, online transactions, operation, paper, party, psak sharia, purchase, qualitative method, reference, sale, seller, system, takaful operation, term.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color covers 22 topics, namely: activity, beginning, behalf, condition, contract, development, dropship system, hawalah, Islamic banking, Islamic finance company, item, kafalah, murabaha financing, muwakkil, online business, order, power, practitioner, property, service contract, supplier, wakalah.
- Cluster 5 The purple color includes 24 topic items, namely: a greeting, bil wakalah, bmt, broker, cash, data collection, disadvantage, fatwa etc. mui no, financing product, good, hybrid contract, murabaha, murabaha financing product, murabaha financing wakalah, murabahah contract, murabahah object, number, observation, person, practice, provision, scale, secondary data, service, village.
- Cluster 6. The light blue color covers 24 topics, namely: a kad wakalah bil ujah, asnaf, claim, company, customer, documentation, effectiveness, health protection product, impact, income, interview, Islamic law, justice, management, national community empowerment program, payment, phb, qualitative research, representative, research sample, sharia, study, type, zakat distribution.
- Cluster 7. The orange color covers 16 topics, namely: a kad wakalah, approach, Indonesian sharia banks, state savings banks, etc., economic transactions, field research, financing, murabahah agreement, PBI, financing, regulation, research methods, Islamic Financial institutions, Medan branch office sharia, validity, wakalah bil ujah contract.
- Cluster 8. The brown color covers 12 topics, namely: b sm e money product, data collection technology, form, harm, literature study, money, murabahah financing, partner outlet, process, sharia economic law, transaction, Wakalah.
- Cluster 9. The dark green color covers 14 topics, namely: authority delegation, concept, fee, field, food, implementation, perspective, requirements, sharia wedding organizer sura, sharia economic law, ujah, value, wakalah bil, wedding exertion.
- Cluster 10. The pink color covers 15 topics, namely: benefit, dsn mui iii, event, fund, kjks mbs, mechanism, muamalah, obligation, participant, product, righth, risk, sharia insurance, tabbaru contract, wakalah bil ujah contract.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Implementation of the Wakalah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 20 research topics regarding the application of the Wakalah to Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, Islamic Financial Institutions. The implementation of the Wakalah at Islamic Financial Institutions can be carried out by obtaining permission from the customer's representative to invest or manage funds in accordance with sharia principles. Financial institutions act as representatives (muwakkil) to carry out transactions on behalf of customers. Muwakkil (customer) gives trust to financial institutions (representatives) to carry out financial activities in accordance with sharia provisions and principles. Representatives are responsible for actions and decisions taken in accordance with the interests of customers.

Second, the Murabaha contract. The implementation of the Murabahah contract is one of the financing mechanisms commonly used in Islamic Financial institutions. This contract involves the sale of goods at the selling price which is added to the previously agreed profit. In the context of delivery services, if there is a need for financing in the process of sending goods, Islamic Financial institutions can use Murabahah contracts to finance the purchase of the required goods or services. The financial institution will buy the goods and then sell them to customers at the agreed price.

Third, delivery service. In the context of delivery services, the application of the Wakalah can be used to establish relationships between service providers and consumers. Consumers can authorize delivery service providers (representatives) to pick up, send or deliver goods or services on their behalf. In this Wakalah, the representative is responsible for carrying out the task of delivering goods or services in accordance with instructions from the consumer. The representative is also responsible for the safety and quality of the goods sent.

Fourth, invest in goods delivery services. In the context of investment in goods delivery services, the implementation of the Wakalah can be used to establish relationships between investors and delivery service companies. Investors authorize the delivery company (deputy) to manage their investment funds. Delivery service companies are responsible for using these investment funds to expand operations, develop infrastructure, or improve goods delivery services. The results of the investment will be shared between the investor and the delivery company according to a previously established agreement.

Fifth, E-Commerce. In the context of E-Commerce, the implementation of the Wakalah can be carried out by the customer giving authority to the platform E-Commerce (representative) to purchase and deliver goods or services on their behalf. Platforms E-Commerce acts as a representative in carrying out transactions on customer instructions. They are responsible for processing purchases, arranging shipping, and handling return or exchange issues according to customer requirements.

Sixth, multi financing. The application of the Wakalah to multi-financing can be done by the customer giving authority to a financial institution or bank (representative) to manage and distribute financing funds to various projects or businesses in need. Financial institutions are responsible for selecting projects or ventures that fit their investment criteria and policies. They will manage and supervise the financing funds on behalf of the customer, as well as monitor the progress of the project or business being financed.

Seventh, distribution of zakat. The application of the Wakalah to the distribution of zakat can be carried out by individuals or zakat bodies

(representatives) being authorized by the muzakki (zakat giver) to collect and distribute the zakat they give. The zakat agency is responsible for managing and distributing zakat in accordance with sharia provisions to mustahik (zakat recipients) who meet the specified criteria. They will act as representatives in managing and distributing zakat funds with transparency and accountability.

Eighth, financing basic necessities. The application of the Wakalah to financing basic necessities can be done by the community giving authority to Islamic Financial institutions or amil zakat bodies (representatives) to purchase and distribute basic necessities to people in need. Financial institutions or zakat amil bodies are responsible for obtaining basic necessities at competitive prices and quality. They will use funds provided by the community to buy basic necessities and organize their distribution to people in need.

Ninth, management of health protection products. The application of the Wakalah in the management of health protection products can be carried out by the customer giving authority to the insurance company or financial institution (representative) to manage and provide health protection services. Insurance companies or financial institutions will use funds collected from customers to pay medical claims and finance the management and administration of health protection programs. They are responsible for managing funds and fulfilling claim obligations in accordance with agreed provisions.

Tenth, sharia insurance products. The application of the Wakalah to sharia insurance products is carried out by the customer giving power to the insurance company (representative) to manage risks and provide protection in accordance with sharia principles. Insurance companies act as representatives to manage funds collected from insurance premiums paid by customers. They are responsible for payment of claims and management of funds in accordance with sharia principles and the provisions of insurance contracts.

Eleventh, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). The implementation of the Wakalah in the context of MSMEs can be carried out by MSMEs giving authority to Islamic Financial institutions (representatives) to manage and provide financing services, financial management or technical assistance to MSMEs. Islamic Financial institutions act as representatives in providing services and support to MSMEs. They can assist in financial management, marketing, product development, or procurement of working capital, according to MSME needs and agreed conditions.

Twelfth, Go-Food. The implementation of the Wakalah on Go-Food services can be done by the customer giving authority to the platform Go-Food (representative) to order, pick up and deliver food or drinks on their behalf. Platforms Go-Food acts as a representative in carrying out food transactions and deliveries. They are responsible for taking orders, delivering on time, and maintaining the quality and safety of the food or drinks delivered.

Thirteenth, holding weddings. The application of the Wakalah in organizing weddings can be done by employing a wedding planner (representative) who acts on behalf of the couple getting married. A wedding planner will act as the couple's representative in organizing and carrying out various wedding preparations, such as vendor selection, scheduling and event coordination. They are responsible for ensuring the wedding runs smoothly according to the couple's wishes.

Fourteenth, platform Sharia Fintech Lending. Implementation of the Wakalah on the platform Sharia Fintech Lending can be done by the customer giving authority to the platform (representative) to manage and provide

financing in accordance with sharia principles. Platforms Sharia Fintech Lending acts as a representative in collecting funds from investors and providing financing to business actors or individuals who need it. They are responsible for managing funds and fulfilling financing obligations in accordance with sharia principles.

Fifteenth, Savings Sukuk (SBSN) product through Fintech. The implementation of the Wakalah on Savings Sukuk (SBSN) products through fintech can be done by the customer giving authority to the fintech platform (representative) to collect funds and manage them in the form of SBSN. The fintech platform acts as a representative in managing funds collected from customers and issuing SBSN. They are responsible for selling and managing SBSN as well as providing profits or rewards to SBSN holders in accordance with agreed conditions.

Sixteenth, online deposit services. The application of the Wakalah to online entrustment services can be done by the customer authorizing the entrustment service provider (representative) to purchase goods or services on their behalf. The entrustment service provider acts as a representative in making purchases based on the customer's instructions. They will purchase goods or services requested by the customer and arrange delivery or pickup of the goods according to the customer's needs.

Seventeenth, Project Based Sukuk. The application of the Wakalah to Project Based Sukuk is carried out by the investor giving authority to the sukuk manager (representative) to manage and invest the sukuk funds in certain projects or investments. The sukuk manager acts as a representative in managing and allocating sukuk funds to predetermined projects or investments. They are responsible for ensuring that sukuk funds are used appropriately according to the project objectives and expected profits.

Eighteenth, Letter of Credit. The application of the Wakalah to a Letter of Credit (L/C) is carried out by the party requiring payment guarantee (muwakkil) giving authority to the bank (representative) to issue an L/C to the party receiving the payment. The bank acts as a representative in issuing an L/C which guarantees payment to the payee if the conditions specified in the L/C are met. The bank is responsible for managing and completing payment transactions on behalf of the muwakkil.

Nineteenth, working capital. The application of the Wakalah to working capital financing is carried out by the business owner or company (muwakkil) giving authority to financial institutions or investors (representatives) to manage and utilize the funds needed for working capital. Financial institutions or investors act as representatives in managing working capital funds provided by the muwakkil. They are responsible for using these funds in operational activities, purchasing supplies, or payroll in accordance with agreed needs and agreements.

Twentieth, People's Business Credit (KUR) financing. The implementation of the Wakalah in People's Business Credit (KUR) financing is carried out by the government or financial institution giving authority to the bank or financial institution (representative) to manage and provide financing to micro, small and medium business actors. Banks or financial institutions act as representatives in providing KUR financing to business actors. They are responsible for managing financing funds, assessing business feasibility, determining the amount of financing, and supervising the use and payment of financing in accordance with applicable regulations.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of the Wakalah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 1 The research topic revolves around the influence of the Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: its influence on loans. The influence of the Wakalah on loans can include several aspects, including:

1. Fund management: In the Wakalah, the loan recipient is responsible for managing the loan funds. Loan recipients can use the funds for business, investment or other agreed purposes. In this case, the effect of the Wakalah on loans is to provide flexibility to loan recipients to manage funds according to their needs.
2. Responsibility and risk: Even though the loan recipient acts as a representative in the Wakalah, he remains fully responsible for the use of loan funds. This means that the loan recipient will bear the risks associated with managing funds, such as investment risk or business risk. The lender is not responsible for the results or losses from the use of these funds, unless there is an error or violation committed by the lender.
3. Profit sharing: In some cases, the Wakalah may also include profit sharing between the lender and the loan recipient. If the loan funds are used for business activities or investments that generate profits, the loan recipient must share a portion of the profits with the lender in accordance with the agreed terms. This can be an incentive for lenders to provide loans in the hope of making additional profits.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Views of Islamic Law, Positive Law and Legislation regarding the Wakalah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 1 1 research topics regarding views of Islamic law, positive law and Wakalah legislation on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, a Wakalah card according to the Koran and Hadith. One of the reasons why al-wakalah is permitted is as stated in the following verse from Allah Ta'ala: "Make me treasurer of the state (Egypt). Indeed, I am a person who is good at guarding and experienced." (Yusuf: 55) In this context, the Prophet Yusuf was willing to become a representative and carry out his mandate as administrator of the Egyptian Federal Reserve. Surah al-Kahf also provides the basis of al-wakalah which is confirmed in the following verse: "And thus We raised them up to ask each other questions among themselves. Said one of them to ask each other, 'How long have you been standing here?' They answered, 'We've been here a day or a day and a half.' Said another, 'Your Lord knows best how long you will be here. So, send one of you to the city with your silver coins and let him see which food is better and let him bring it to you, and let him be gentle, and never tell anyone about you.'" (Al-Kahfi:19) This verse describes one of the ash-habul kahfi who acts as a representative on behalf of his colleagues in choosing and purchasing food in a gentle manner, while maintaining the confidentiality of their identity. Meanwhile, in the hadith, namely: in everyday life, Rasulullah Shallallahu 'Alaihi Wasallam often entrusted his tasks to other people. One of them was when he asked Abu Rafi' and an Ansar to represent him in his marriage to Maimunah bint Harith. Apart from that, in everyday life, the Prophet also often asked other people to pay his debts, set and pay limits, take care of camels, divide animal pens, and various other tasks.

Second, a Wakalah card according to ulama. Hashbi Ash Shiddieqy believes that Wakalah is an agreement to transfer power in which a person appoints another person as his successor in acting. According to Sayyid Sabiq, Wakalah is someone's action to transfer their power to another person in matters that can be represented. Malikiyah scholars define Wakalah as the action of a person who represents himself to another person to carry out actions that are within his rights, but is not related to the granting of power of attorney after death, because if it is related to actions after death, it will become a will. The view of the Shafi'iah Ulama states that Wakalah is the process of delegating something by someone to another person so that the other person carries out what can be authorized in the name of the person giving the authority. Hanafiah scholars explain Wakalah as the act of someone entrusting another person to act as his substitute in certain areas that can be represented.

Third, the Istismar bill according to DSN-MUI. Wakalah bil Istismar is a term used by the National Sharia Council-Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) to refer to Wakalahs relating to the management of investment funds or capital. In this context, the representative acts as a manager of funds or assets owned by the mandate. According to DSN-MUI, the Wakalah bil Istismar contract must comply with sharia principles, such as an agreement between both parties, clarity in objectives and instructions, and fair distribution of results based on the initial agreement. DSN-MUI also provides guidelines regarding the practices and procedures for implementing the Wakalah bil Istismar contract in accordance with applicable sharia principles.

Fourth, accounting for the Wakalah according to PSAK 103, 108. PSAK 103 (Statement of Financial Accounting Standards) and PSAK 108 are accounting standards issued by the Indonesian Financial Accounting Standards Board (DSAK). PSAK 103, entitled "Accounting for Wakalah," and PSAK 108, entitled "Accounting for Agents, Distributors, and Franchisees," provide guidance on how to account for and report transactions involving Wakalahs. According to PSAK 103 and 108, entities acting as representatives (agents, distributors, or franchisees) must recognize and measure Wakalah transactions in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles. Transactions in a Wakalah are considered as separate transactions between the entity and the owner or mandator. This standard provides guidance regarding the disclosure of relevant information regarding Wakalahs, the responsibilities of the parties involved, the financial impact of Wakalah transactions, as well as disclosure of risks and uncertainties related to these contracts. PSAK 103 and 108 aim to ensure that the financial reports prepared by the entity reflect the transactions and events that occur in the Wakalah accurately and transparently.

Fifth, a Wakalah card according to DSN-MUI. Wakalah is a contract in Islamic law in which a party (muwakkil) gives authority to another party (representative) to carry out actions or transactions on his behalf. The representative acts on the basis of trust and responsibility to carry out the tasks given by the muwakkil. In the Wakalah, the muwakkil is responsible for the results of actions or transactions carried out by the representative, unless the representative violates the agreed terms.

Sixth, a Wakalah card according to Islamic law / fiqh. In Islamic law, the Wakalah is a form of syirkah (partnership) contract which is used to carry out certain tasks. In this contract, the muwakkil gives authority to the representative to carry out actions or transactions on his behalf. The deputy acts as an extension of the muwakkil and is responsible for carrying out the tasks assigned in accordance with the muwakkil's instructions and interests.

Muwakkil remains responsible for the results of actions or transactions carried out by the representative, unless there is an error or negligence made by the representative.

Seventh, a Wakalah card according to the Islamic economic system. In the Islamic economic system, the Wakalah has an important role in economic activities. This contract is used to give authority to individuals or institutions to carry out economic functions on behalf of other people or groups. In the context of the Islamic economic system, the Wakalah is used in various transactions such as buying and selling, investment, asset management, and so on. The main principles of the Wakalah in the Islamic economic system are trust (amanah), honesty and fairness in its implementation.

Eighth, a Wakalah card according to the rules of economic jurisprudence. In economic jurisprudence, a Wakalah is defined as a contract that allows a person or business entity to act as a representative in carrying out certain transactions or tasks on behalf of another party. This contract involves the transfer of authority to a representative to manage certain affairs or transactions in accordance with predetermined provisions and instructions. In economic jurisprudence, the Wakalah is regulated by the principles of jurisprudence which include the terms, rights, obligations and responsibilities of both parties involved in the contract.

Ninth, sales of financing guarantees for the Murabahah Bil Wakalah. The sale of financing guarantees in the Murabahah Bil Wakalah refers to transactions involving the sale of guarantees or collateral to support financing based on Murabahah principles. In this contract, the seller (bank or financial institution) acts as a representative or representative of the buyer (customer) to carry out collateral or collateral sales transactions. This sale of collateral is carried out with the aim of protecting the interests of banks or financial institutions in providing financing based on Murabahah principles.

Tenth, a Wakalah bil Ujrah card. The Wakalah bil Ujrah contract refers to a wakalah or representation agreement with payment of remuneration or ujrah. In this contract, a person or entity (representative) is given the authority to act on behalf of another person or entity (wakalah) with certain rewards or compensation. In the context of Islamic banking and finance, the Wakalah bil Ujrah contract is often used to give authority to banks or financial institutions to act as representatives or representatives of customers in carrying out certain transactions or activities.

Eleventh, default on the Murabahah Bil Wakalah. Default on the Murabahah Bil Wakalah refers to a violation or failure to fulfill the obligations agreed upon in the Murabahah Bil Wakalah. Default can occur if one party does not fulfill the commitments or obligations agreed upon in the agreement. For example, if a bank or financial institution as a representative does not convey correctly or does not take actions that should be carried out in accordance with the Murabahah Bil Wakalah agreement, this can be considered a breach of contract.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Wakalah Development Efforts

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 3 research topic regarding efforts to develop Wakalahs for Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

Fintech-based Wakalah bil Ujrah contract. Fintech-based Wakalah bil Ujrah contracts refer to agreements that use financial technology (fintech) to facilitate

Wakalah bil Ujrah transactions. Wakalah bil Ujrah is a Wakalah that involves the payment of ujrah (fee) or commission to a representative or fund manager (deputy), who acts on behalf of the trustor or fund owner (muwakkil). In the context of fintech, technology is used to simplify and automate transaction processes and monitor Wakalahs electronically. In the Fintech-based Wakalah bil Ujrah contract, the fintech platform acts as an intermediary between the muwakkil and the representative. This platform provides infrastructure and systems that enable muwakkil to carry out transactions and manage funds easily and efficiently. For example, a fintech platform may offer an application or website that allows muwakkil to select representatives, set investment parameters, and monitor their portfolio performance in real-time.

Side Streaming on Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing. Side Streaming in Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing refers to the additional mechanism used in Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing. Murabahah Bil Wakalah is a form of sharia financing that involves a Murabahah contract (purchase of commodities with a markup) and a Wakalah (appointment of a representative to carry out the transaction). In Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing, Side Streaming is an agreement that allows other third parties (other than muwakkil and representatives) to participate in the transaction. In this context, the third party is usually a bank or financial institution that provides additional funds to facilitate transactions. This third party can act as an initial seller who buys commodities from other sources, then sells them back to the muwakkil with a certain markup or margin. With side streaming, Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing can involve more than two parties, thereby expanding access to wider sources of funds.

Wakalah application on BSM E-Money products. The application of the Wakalah in BSM E-Money products refers to the use of the Wakalah in the development of BSM E-Money products by Bank Syariah Mandiri (BSM). BSM E-Money is an electronic-based financial product that allows users to make non-cash payments and transactions easily. In this context, the Wakalah is used to carry out BSM E-Money product operations. Bank Syariah Mandiri acts as a representative or fund manager (deputy), while the BSM E-Money holder acts as a trustee or fund owner (muwakkil). Basically, BSM E-Money users entrust their funds to BSM as a representative, who then manages them to facilitate electronic payment transactions. Through the Wakalah, BSM E-Money can be operated with appropriate sharia principles, such as justice, transparency and the prohibition of usury. By using this agreement, BSM E-Money can offer sharia-compliant electronic payment solutions to their customers.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues Related to the Wakalah

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 12 research topics around other issues related to the Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely:

First, Shariah Compliance in the Wakalah. Shariah Compliance in the Wakalah refers to compliance with sharia principles in the implementation of the Wakalah. Wakalah is an agreement in which a power of attorney (muwakkil) authorizes an agent (representative) to carry out actions or transactions on his behalf. In the context of sharia finance, Wakalahs are often used in various products, such as insurance and investment. To be in accordance with sharia principles, the Wakalah must meet several requirements. First, the purpose of the contract must be clear and valid according to sharia. Second, all parties

involved in the contract must have honest intentions and no elements of fraud. Third, assets managed by the representative must be separated from the representative's personal assets. Fourth, the representative must act within the limits of the powers granted by the principal. Fifth, the distribution of rewards or commissions to representatives must be in accordance with the principles of sharia justice.

Second, musytari protection against standard clauses in Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing. Murabahah Bil Wakalah is a form of sharia financing where a bank or financial institution acts as a representative to purchase assets needed by clients, then sells them to clients at pre-agreed prices with a profit margin added. In Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing, there are standard clauses which are usually stated in the agreement between the bank and the client. Protection of musytari, namely the parties who obtain financing, against these standard clauses is important so as not to harm them. Standard clauses are standard provisions that have been prepared in advance by the financing provider and tend to benefit the financing provider. Therefore, musytari need to get legal protection so that they are not trapped in provisions that are detrimental to them. Sharia principles emphasize balance and fairness in contracts, so legal protection must ensure that the standard clauses used do not violate these principles.

Third, legal protection for life insurance policy holders in the Wakalah bil Ujrah contract. In the Wakalah bil Ujrah contract, which is used in sharia life insurance, the policy holder (muwakkil) authorizes the insurance company (representative) to manage and invest the premiums paid by the policy holder. Wakalah bil Ujrah refers to a Wakalah with the payment of remuneration or ujrah as a reward to the representative. Legal protection for life insurance policy holders is important to ensure fairness and security in the implementation of the contract. Policy holders must obtain clear and accurate information about the benefits, risks and conditions related to life insurance policies. Apart from that, legal protection must also guarantee that the insurance company carries out the contract in good faith and does not violate sharia principles in managing the entrusted premiums.

Fourth, compare the Wakalah bil Ujrah contract with the Qardh contract. The Wakalah bil Ujrah contract and the Qardh contract are two types of contracts used in the context of sharia finance. The difference between the two lies in the nature of the transaction. The Wakalah bil Ujrah contract is a Wakalah with the payment of ujrah or remuneration to a representative who acts on behalf of the owner of the funds. In this contract, the owner of the funds authorizes the representative to manage and invest the funds for a certain fee. Meanwhile, the Qardh contract is a loan agreement without compensation. In a Qardh contract, the lender provides a loan to the borrower without expecting anything in return or interest. The borrower only needs to return the amount lent. Thus, the main difference between the Wakalah bil Ujrah contract and the Qardh contract lies in the presence of compensation or ujrah in the Wakalah bil Ujrah contract, while the Qardh contract does not involve compensation or interest.

Fifth, the concept of justice in the Murabahah Bil Wakalah. In the Murabahah Bil Wakalah, justice is one of the main principles that must be adhered to. Murabahah Bil Wakalah is a form of sharia financing where a bank or financial institution acts as a representative to purchase assets needed by a client, then sells them to the client at a pre-agreed price with a profit margin added. The concept of justice in this contract involves several aspects. First, the

price agreed between the bank and the client must be reasonable and fair, reflecting the real value of the assets purchased and a reasonable profit margin. Second, information regarding prices and profit margins must be transparent and clear to clients, so they can make informed decisions. In addition, justice also involves separation between bank assets and client assets. The bank as a representative must keep client assets and bank assets clearly separated, so that no misuse or misappropriation occurs which is detrimental to either party.

Sixth, the concept of moral hazard in the Al-Wakalah Murabahah Agreement. Moral hazard refers to the risk that arises when one party, in this context the party who obtains financing in a Murabahah Al-Wakalah, takes a higher risk because they feel protected by another party, in this case a bank or financial institution. In Murabahah Al-Wakalahs, moral hazard can occur when the party obtaining financing tends to take disproportionate or excessive risks because they know that the bank or financial institution will bear most of the financial risk. Those who obtain financing may ignore the principle of prudence in the use of funds or take greater risks for their personal gain, because they will not bear the full consequences of failure or loss. To overcome moral hazard, there needs to be an effective monitoring and control mechanism. Banks or financial institutions need to carry out careful risk assessments and ensure that parties obtaining financing are aware of their responsibilities and obligations in managing entrusted funds.

Seventh, empowerment of Sukuk Wakalah in Islamic finance. Wakalah Sukuk is a Islamic Financial instrument that combines Wakalah principles with sukuk issuance. Sukuk are certificates that provide ownership of the assets or projects that are used as the basis for financing. In Sukuk Wakalah, the sukuk issuer acts as a representative who manages assets or projects on behalf of the sukuk holder. Empowerment of Sukuk Wakalah in Islamic finance includes several aspects.

1. Sukuk Wakalah provides an opportunity for investors to participate in sharia-compliant financing of projects or assets by avoiding usury or interest. This allows the development of a wider Islamic capital market.
2. Wakalah Sukuk enable investment diversification and more efficient fund allocation in Islamic finance. Sukuk holders can choose to invest in projects or assets that suit their risk profile and preferences.
3. Sukuk Wakalah empowerment also includes infrastructure and economic development. By issuing sukuk to finance infrastructure projects, countries or institutions can collect funds from investors which are then used for development and improvement of infrastructure which is important for economic growth.

Eighth, the agency concept of sharia banks and MSMEs in Murabahah wal Wakalah financing. The concept of agency in the context of Murabahah wal Wakalah financing refers to the relationship between sharia banks as agents and MSMEs as principals. Sharia banks act as agents who manage and run financing according to the needs of MSMEs as principals. In this agency relationship, there are several challenges that need to be overcome.

1. Islamic banks must act with honesty, integrity and good faith in carrying out their duties as agents. They must ensure that the funds provided by MSMEs are used appropriately in accordance with the agreement and financing objectives.
2. MSMEs as principals need to provide accurate and transparent information to Islamic banks so that banks can carry out good risk assessments. MSMEs must also maintain the trust of sharia banks by

complying with the provisions and obligations in the financing agreement. Apart from that, Islamic banks also need to provide support and guidance to MSMEs in developing their businesses. This can include training, consultation and access to networks that can help MSMEs grow and develop. By paying attention to this agency concept, Murabahah wal Wakalah financing can run more effectively and profitably for both Islamic banks and MSMEs.

Ninth, abuse of the Wakalah and its control. Abuse of the Wakalah can occur when the party acting as a representative violates the provisions and principles of sharia in carrying out their duties. Some forms of abuse that may occur are the use of wakalah funds for personal interests, ignoring instructions from the power of attorney, or abuse of authority in managing assets. To prevent this abuse, there needs to be an effective control mechanism. This could include:

1. Transparency: The party acting as a representative must provide clear and accurate information to the principal regarding the use of funds and the results of actions taken as a representative.
2. Supervision: The principal or related interested parties must exercise effective supervision over the actions and decisions taken by the proxy. This may involve audits, periodic reporting, or independent inspections.
3. Clear Contract Agreement: The Wakalah must contain clear provisions regarding the rights and obligations of both parties, limitations on the authority of the representative, and a dispute resolution mechanism if a dispute occurs.
4. Education and Awareness: The parties involved in a Wakalah must have an adequate understanding of sharia principles and their responsibilities. Education and awareness will help prevent abuse and promote practices that comply with sharia principles.

Tenth, deviation from buying and selling transactions to service transactions. Deviations from buying and selling transactions to service transactions can occur in the context of a Wakalah if there is an unreasonable use or misuse of the Wakalah concept. In a valid Wakalah, the relationship between the principal and the representative is based on the concept of buying and selling (buying and selling) by granting authority to the representative to carry out these actions on behalf of the principal. However, irregularities can occur if the Wakalah is misused to disguise service transactions that should involve different contracts, such as service contracts or loan contracts. This can be done to avoid provisions or prohibitions in buying and selling transactions, or to obtain benefits that are not permitted by sharia. To prevent this deviation, it is important to ensure transparency and honesty in the Wakalah. The parties involved must understand the limitations and conditions related to the contract, and carry out it in good faith and in accordance with sharia principles.

Eleventh, hybrid contract Murabahah Bil Wakalah. The Murabahah Bil Wakalah hybrid contract is a combination of two types of contracts, namely the Murabahah contract and the Wakalah. In this hybrid contract, the bank or financial institution acts as a representative who purchases the assets needed by the client and then sells them to the client at a pre-agreed price with a profit margin added. The Murabahah Bil Wakalah combines the characteristics of both contracts. Murabahah contracts form the basis of asset buying and selling transactions, while Wakalahs give authority to banks or financial institutions to act on behalf of clients in carrying out these transactions. The advantage of the Murabahah Bil Wakalah hybrid contract is that it allows flexibility in the

financing structure. This can meet the different needs and preferences of clients and take into account applicable sharia provisions and requirements.

Twelfth, comparison of the concept and application of the Wakalah. The concept of the Wakalah is based on sharia principles which regulate the relationship between the principal and the representative. The application of the Wakalah can occur in various contexts and Islamic Financial products, such as insurance, investment or financing. Differences in the application of the Wakalah depend on the type of transaction or product involving the contract. For example, in sharia insurance, the Wakalah is used to authorize the insurance company as a representative to manage and invest the premiums paid by the policy holder. In the context of financing, Wakalahs are often used in Murabahah Bil Wakalah financing where banks or financial institutions act as representatives to buy and sell assets to clients with a profit margin. Although the concept of the Wakalah remains the same, its implementation can vary depending on the type of transaction, product and regulations that apply in each country or Islamic Financial institution. It is important to ensure that the implementation of the Wakalah is in accordance with sharia principles, transparent and fair for all parties involved.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 5 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Wakalahs in Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application of Wakalahs; (2) The effect of the Wakalah; (3) Views of Islamic law, positive law and legislation surrounding the Wakalah; (4) Efforts to develop the Wakalah; and (5) Other issues related to the Wakalah.

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